

Supplementary Information for “Beating your neighbor to the berry patch” [3]

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S1 Simulations with uncertainty

The theory presented in the main text assumes that all foragers value the resource equally, and none have any private information about its value. To investigate the model’s sensitivity to these assumptions, I compared it against two simulations.

Each simulation mimics a model drawn from the literature on auctions [2]. In the *common value* model, the value of the resource is not known with certainty, but each forager has an independent estimate. For example, when hummingbirds compete for nectar from a flower, each bird knows the time of its own last visit to the flower but does not know about visits by other birds [1]. Thus, each bird has a private signal about the flower’s quality, but no bird knows the quality with certainty. In the *private values* model, the caloric value of the resource is common knowledge, but each forager values these calories differently. For example, a starving forager and one well fed might value the same strawberry very differently.

To model these interactions, I assume as before that foragers choose a value v at which to visit the resource and that the forager with the lowest value gets the resource. The return to a successful forager, however, is not v , but Yv , where Y is a random variable with a distribution that is uniform on the interval $[0.7, 1.3)$. This introduces a substantial uncertainty, since the range of Y is 60% of its mean. In these models, v is no longer the value of the resource at the time of the forager’s visit. I will refer to it as the resource’s “*ex ante* value” to indicate that it is the expected value before any private signal is received. In the private values model, an independent value of Y is drawn for each forager, and this value is revealed to the forager as a private signal. In the common value model, an independent value of Y is drawn for each group of $K + 1$ competing foragers, and each forager receives a signal $s = uY$, where u is uniform on $[0, 1)$ and an independent value of u is drawn for each forager. In either model, each forager determines its behavior by consulting its own “response function.”

Response functions are piece-wise linear with six parameters. Figure S1 shows the response functions of two foragers, one indicated by open circles and the other by bold dots. The signal is on the horizontal axis. The vertical positions of the symbols indicate the values of the six parameters in each forager’s response function. Each function is constructed by connecting the symbols with straight lines. When the value of the response function exceeds 1.3 (the maximum value that the resource can have), the forager does not visit the resource. Thus, the forager whose function is indicated by open circles never visits the resource at all. When the response is less than 1.3, its value is taken to equal v , the *ex ante* value of the resource at the time of the forager’s visit. Thus,

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Figure S1: Piecewise linear response functions

The private signal is on the horizontal axis, and the forager’s response v is on the vertical axis. When $v \geq 1.3$, the forager does not visit the resource and therefore pays no cost. When $v < 1.3$, the forager visits the resource when its *ex ante* expected value is v . The function indicated by open circles describes a forager who never visits the resource, and the function indicated by bold dots describes a forager who always visits the resource.

the forager indicated by bold dots always visits the resource. Mutation acts by perturbing the value of each parameter in the response function. Offspring inherit the response functions of their (single) parent.

Figures S2 and S3 show the results of simulations under the common value model and the private values model, respectively. In each case, the parameter values are identical to those in figure 5 of the main text. The theory presented in the main text ignores the uncertainty inherent in these simulations but nonetheless does a good job of predicting their behavior. The fit of the common value model could hardly be better. Under the private values model, the aggregate distribution fits much better than the distribution of the final generation. Nonetheless, the theoretical model is remarkably accurate even where its assumptions are not met.

References

- [1] Frank B. Gill. “Trapline Foraging by Hermit Hummingbirds: Competition for an undefended Renewable Resource”. In: *Ecology* 69.6 (1988), pp. 1933–1942. DOI: 10.2307/1941170.
- [2] Dan Levin and James L. Smith. “Equilibrium in Auctions with Entry”. In: *The American Economic Review* 84.3 (June 1994), pp. 585–599. eprint: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/2118069>.
- [3] Alan R. Rogers. “Beating Your Neighbor to the Berry Patch”. In: *Peer Community Journal* 133 (2022). DOI: 10.24072/pcjournal.133.

Figure S2: Simulation under the common value model

The simulation uses 5000 groups and assumes $c = 0.3$ and $K = 3$, so $2^K c = 2.4 > 1$, and the Nash equilibrium resists invasion by pure strategies. In the bottom panel, the aggregate distribution (circles) summarizes 6,530,751 individuals, and the final distribution (stars) summarizes 6386.

Figure S3: Simulation under the private value model

The simulation uses 5000 groups and assumes that $c = 0.3$ and $K = 3$, so the Nash equilibrium resists invasion by pure strategies. In the bottom panel, the aggregate distribution (circles) summarizes 6,759,231 individuals, and the final distribution (stars) summarizes 6695.